

Diffusion-based data augmentation for short-term multivariate energy prediction in data-scarce scenarios

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Abstract—Accuracy in short-term energy forecasting is crucial for a wide range of energy prediction tasks, but remains challenging when historical data are scarce due to complex temporal dependencies and multivariate interactions. This study explores diffusion-based generative modeling as a data augmentation strategy to improve forecasting in data-scarce scenarios. Using the ETTh1 multivariate energy dataset, we evaluate point and quantile forecasting across multiple forecasting architectures (XGBoost, LSTM, BiLSTM). Synthetic samples are generated via the Diffusion-TS framework for the neural models only, and incorporated at varying synthetic-to-real ratios. Results show that BiLSTM models benefit substantially in point forecasting, achieving up to a 15.3% improvement (i.e., reduction) in RMSE and 8.1% in MAE, and similarly improve quantile accuracy, while LSTM models degrade under all ratios. Bias-variance analysis reveals that diffusion-based augmentation mainly reduces variance at moderate levels but introduces bias when excessive synthetic data are used.

I. INTRODUCTION

Accuracy in short-term energy forecasting remains challenging due to complex temporal dynamics and nonlinear interactions among multiple influencing factors. For forecasting models to be effective, they must capture both time-dependent behavior and cross-feature relationships to produce reliable predictions. Two common forecasting techniques are *point forecasting (PF)*, which predicts a single expected value, and *quantile forecasting (QF)*, which estimates conditional distributions at different probability levels.

To address multivariate temporal dependencies, both machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models are used: XGBoost [1] for nonlinear features, and recurrent architectures such as LSTM [2] and BiLSTM [3] for sequential dependencies.

Despite their modeling capacity, DL approaches are often limited by the scarcity of large, high-quality datasets. Unlike other fields such as computer vision or natural language processing, energy forecasting typically relies on domain-specific data of limited scope, which constrains model generalization. This has driven an interest in techniques that can mitigate data scarcity and improve robustness.

A promising direction involves *data augmentation* using generative models that are able to synthesize diverse and realistic samples to enrich the training distribution. Among

these, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [4] have shown strong performance in image and speech generation, but typically suffer from mode collapse and training instability [5]. Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) [6] offer a more stable optimization via explicit likelihood modeling, but often sacrifice the sharpness of the generated samples.

Recently, diffusion-based generative models [7] have emerged as a robust alternative. They formulate the generation as a gradual denoising process, and the diffusion models can produce diverse and highly realistic samples and have become state-of-the-art across multiple domains. Their training stability and generative quality motivate exploration for data augmentation in time-series forecasting.

Building on these advances, this study adopts a two-phase framework (Fig. 1). In the first phase, we establish PF and QF baselines using ML and DL models. In the second phase, we apply a diffusion-based data augmentation strategy to generate synthetic multivariate time-series samples. Because the diffusion model’s outputs naturally take a 3D array format, they integrate seamlessly with sequence models such as LSTM and BiLSTM, while being less suited to tree-based models like XGBoost.

This work addresses the data-scarce challenge while demonstrating an end-to-end pipeline of synthetic data (SD) generation into a downstream forecasting pipeline. Unlike previous works that focus on the generation of the SD solely, we directly evaluate how SD affects forecasting performance. Through this framework, we aim to enhance short-term energy forecasting under data-scarce conditions and highlight the broader potential of diffusion-based augmentation for real-world time-series applications.

II. RELATED WORK

ML methods such as gradient boosting and random forests have been extensively applied in short-term energy forecasting due to their ability to model nonlinear feature relationships [8], [9]. Among them, XGBoost remains one of the most widely used baselines across forecasting tasks including electricity load, solar generation, and wind power prediction [10], [11]. More recently, the increased adoption of DL has led to significant improvements in short-term forecasting accuracy. Architectures such as recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and their variants, LSTM and BiLSTM, have been used to model long-range dependencies and seasonality in energy time-series data [12]–[14].

In parallel, research on time-series synthetic data generation has evolved from statistical resampling techniques to modern generative models. Traditional methods such as

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Fig. 1. Overview of the full experimental pipeline

bootstrapping or autoregressive models (e.g., ARIMA) are limited in their capacity to capture nonlinear temporal dependencies and multivariate correlations, which are typical in energy data [15], [16]. Generative modeling provides a promising alternative by learning the underlying data distribution and synthesizing new, realistic samples that extend limited datasets.

Among generative techniques, GANs have been widely explored for synthetic time-series generation. Early efforts such as RCGAN [17] employed a recurrent conditional architecture to generate real-valued sequences, demonstrating the potential of GANs for structured temporal data. TimeGAN [18] further combined adversarial and supervised objectives to preserve temporal dynamics and latent dependencies. More recently, GT-GAN [19] introduced a general-purpose framework for multivariate time-series synthesis, emphasizing scalability and the preservation of feature-wise dependencies. Despite these advances, GAN-based models often remain sensitive to training hyperparameters and struggle to maintain long-term temporal coherence, limiting their reliability for structured time-series augmentation.

VAEs offer more stable optimization through explicit likelihood modeling, as seen in TimeVAE [20], but often produce overly smooth or low-variance sequences that reduce temporal fidelity.

Recently, diffusion-based generative models have emerged as a robust alternative [7], [21]. By progressively denoising noise-corrupted data, diffusion models learn to capture complex dependencies and generate high-fidelity samples with superior stability compared to GANs or VAEs. Their application to time-series data has shown promising results. TS-Diffusion [22] demonstrated that diffusion models can effectively generate highly complex temporal patterns and capture long-term dependencies across diverse sequence types. Likewise, Diffusion-TS [23] proposed a diffusion-based framework for multivariate time-series synthesis, emphasizing improved temporal coherence and cross-feature dependency modeling.

Despite these advances, most prior works evaluate gener-

ative models in isolation, focusing on synthetic data quality rather than their downstream impact on forecasting performance. To bridge this gap, our study integrates the Diffusion-TS framework directly into a short-term energy forecasting pipeline, systematically assessing how varying proportions of synthetic data influence model generalization across both point and quantile forecasting tasks under a data-scarce scenario.

III. DATASET

A. Description

The experiments use the ETTh1 dataset [24], a multivariate energy time-series benchmark for long-term electricity transformer temperature forecasting. It contains two years of hourly data from two Chinese counties, including the target variable (*oil temperature*) and six power load features. For computational efficiency, we adopt the ETT-small subset, which includes data from two transformers at two stations.

B. Preprocessing

The dataset comprises regularly sampled multivariate time-series measurements, representing multiple correlated variables observed at consistent time intervals. To enhance temporal representation, we engineer cyclical time features (*hour of day*, *day of week*) using sine and cosine transformations and include lag features of the target variable. The data are split into training, validation, and test sets using an 85%/5%/10% ratio, applied consistently across all models. Each feature is scaled independently using a *StandardScaler* fitted on the training set.

For DL models (LSTM and BiLSTM), inputs are prepared via a sliding window with a lookback of 168 hours (one week) and a prediction horizon of one step, as suggested by the autocorrelation of the target variable. In contrast, XGBoost operates on flattened, non-sequential input representations.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the overall methodology, including the baseline model training, evaluation procedure, and the proposed data augmentation approach.

TABLE I
QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION METRICS FOR DIFFUSION-TS ON THE DATASET.

Metric	Score
Discriminative score	0.1442 ± 0.1211
Predictive score	0.0524 ± 0.0011
KL Divergence score	0.0315 ± 0.0232
Wasserstein Distance score	0.0078 ± 0.0038

The selected architectures, XGBoost, LSTM, and BiLSTM, were implemented using established frameworks. Hyperparameters were tuned on the ETTh1 dataset and fixed across all experiments to ensure comparability and reproducibility.¹

A. Model Training

In this work, models used an 85%/5%/10% train-val-test split ratio. To account for stochasticity in DL models, each configuration was trained with five random seeds (42, 4242, 1234, 2021, 777), and performance was averaged across seeds to ensure robustness. Evaluation considered multiple metrics, with RMSE and MAE serving as primary measures due to their prevalence in energy forecasting [25]. In the final testing stage, models were retrained on the combined training and validation set, and results were reported on the held-out test set.

B. Synthetic Data Generation

To address data scarcity, we employ the Diffusion-TS framework for synthetic time-series generation. In this work, only the unconstrained mode is used to produce new sequences resembling the original energy data, which are later integrated into the forecasting pipeline.

Evaluating SD quality is critical, yet no universal standard exists. A recent survey [26] identified over 80 metrics for assessing fidelity and utility, emphasizing the need for complementary approaches. Accordingly, SD quality is evaluated through both qualitative and quantitative analyses.

Qualitative evaluation uses *t*-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) to visually compare distributions of real and synthetic samples. Quantitative evaluation incorporates four established metrics: Discriminative Score, Predictive Score, Kullback–Leibler (KL) Divergence, and Wasserstein Distance, following recommended practices for time-series generation [26].

Time-related cyclical features (hour of day and day of week) are included as contextual variables in the generation

process but excluded from quantitative analysis to avoid distortion in distance-based metrics. KL divergence is computed on unnormalized data to preserve probabilistic structure, while Wasserstein distance uses normalized values within [0,1].

Fig. 2. Principal Component Analysis plot

Fig. 3. *t*-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding plot

Regarding augmentation, SD are added at ratios of 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0 relative to the real dataset and used only with neural models during testing. Each configuration is trained with five seeds for consistency with the baseline procedure. Evaluation follows the same protocol as for baseline models, using both PF and QF metrics.

V. RESULTS

Before evaluating the forecasting performance, we first assess the quality of the SD generated by the Diffusion-TS framework. Fig. 2–4 illustrate the qualitative comparisons between real and synthetic samples. The PCA and t-SNE visualizations show strong spatial overlap between distributions, indicating that the SD capture the overall temporal structure of the original dataset. Similarly, the KDE plot reveals close alignment in marginal distributions, suggesting

¹<https://github.com/it21346/CAI-2026-diff-aug>

Fig. 4. Kernel Density Estimation plot

that Diffusion-TS preserves data density and range characteristics. Quantitative evaluation (Table I) further supports these findings, with low discriminative and predictive scores indicating realistic and utility-preserving samples, and small KL divergence and Wasserstein distance values confirming statistical similarity. Overall, these results demonstrate that Diffusion-TS produces synthetic sequences with high fidelity and suitable realism for data augmentation.

After establishing data quality, we evaluate the effect of incorporating SD into model training. The analysis investigates whether augmentation improves forecasting accuracy, how its impact varies across architectures (excluding XGBoost), and whether gains follow monotonic or non-monotonic trends as the synthetic ratio increases. We also interpret results through the lens of the bias–variance trade-off to understand why unidirectional and bidirectional architectures respond differently.

Two forecasting tasks are considered: (i) **PF**, which predicts a single deterministic future value, and (ii) **QF**, which estimates conditional quantiles (e.g., $q=0.05$, $q=0.5$, $q=0.95$) to capture predictive uncertainty. In PF, we use **RMSE**, **MAE**, **MSE**, **SMAPE**, while in QF, we add **Pinball loss** for probabilistic accuracy.

To quantify relative improvement or degradation, we define the **Improvement Ratio (IR)**, expressing the percentage change in performance from augmentation relative to the baseline model:

$$\overline{\text{Metric}}_{\text{aug}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{s=1}^N \text{Metric}_{\text{aug},s}, \quad (1)$$

$$\overline{\text{Metric}}_{\text{base}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{s=1}^N \text{Metric}_{\text{base},s}, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{IR}(\%) = \frac{\overline{\text{Metric}}_{\text{base}} - \overline{\text{Metric}}_{\text{aug}}}{\overline{\text{Metric}}_{\text{base}}} \times 100, \quad (3)$$

where $\overline{\text{Metric}}_{\text{base}}$ and $\overline{\text{Metric}}_{\text{aug}}$ denote the mean metric values computed across all random seeds s , and N is the total number of seed runs used for averaging (in this study, $N=5$).

IR results for **PF** are shown in Table II, while those for **QF**, including Pinball losses at $q=0.05$, $q=0.5$, and $q=0.95$, appear in Table III.

To further interpret the observed trends, we decompose model errors into bias and variance components (Tables IV and V). This analysis helps identify whether diffusion-based augmentation primarily reduces variance (by mitigating overfitting) or increases bias (through distributional shifts).

Finally, baseline performances and best-performing augmentation ratios are summarized for both forecasting paradigms in Tables VI and VII.

A. Discussion

The observed effects of diffusion-based data augmentation can also be interpreted through the lens of model capacity and the bias–variance trade-off.

For **PF**, the two recurrent architectures exhibit distinct responses to synthetic augmentation. The BiLSTM model shows a generally monotonic improvement in forecasting accuracy as the proportion of SD increases up to $n=0.5$, after which performance deteriorates sharply at $n=0.75$ before recovering for most metrics at $n=1.0$. The corresponding bias–variance decomposition supports this interpretation: both bias and variance decrease up to $n=0.5$, indicating that BiLSTM benefits from synthetic regularization, whereas variance spikes again at $n=0.75$.

In contrast, the LSTM model consistently underperforms across all synthetic ratios, with IR values remaining negative throughout. Both bias and variance increase monotonically, suggesting that the model fails to adapt effectively to the augmented data distribution. This suggests LSTM’s lower capacity makes it more sensitive to distributional shifts, leading to systematic degradation rather than regularization. Consequently, diffusion-based augmentation appears beneficial only for the more expressive BiLSTM within this PF framework.

For **QF**, BiLSTM again demonstrates clear benefits, though the strongest improvements occur at the highest synthetic ratio ($n=1.0$), where both bias and variance decrease noticeably across most error-based metrics. This suggests that full synthetic training may enhance calibration when estimating conditional quantiles, possibly due to the smoother distribution learned by the diffusion model.

The LSTM model, on the other hand, displays similar behavior to its PF case, showing a generally monotonic degradation in forecasting accuracy as the synthetic ratio increases. This is also reflected in the bias–variance decomposition, where bias increases steadily even as variance decreases, indicating that the additional SD fail to improve generalization. Here, the LSTM model exhibits an inverse bias–variance trend: as the proportion of SD increases, bias steadily rises while variance decreases. This pattern suggests that the synthetic samples act as a strong regularizer, constraining the model’s predictions and reducing variability across training runs, but at the cost of introducing systematic error. In other words, the LSTM becomes more stable yet increasingly biased toward the SD distribution, indicating

TABLE II

IR (%) ACROSS ALL MODEL/SCALER/BATCH CONFIGURATIONS (PF). POSITIVE = IMPROVEMENT.

Model	Scaler	Batch	Metric	Synthetic-to-Real Ratio (n)					Best (%) \uparrow
				0.10	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	
BiLSTM	standard	64	SMAPE	3.6\pm17.4%	0.0 \pm 30.0%	-3.3 \pm 29.9%	-13.7 \pm 39.9%	2.9 \pm 24.8%	3.6%
BiLSTM	standard	64	RMSE	4.6 \pm 34.5%	3.1 \pm 66.2%	18.9\pm39.9%	1.8 \pm 71.5%	15.3 \pm 44.7%	18.9%
BiLSTM	standard	64	MAE	5.5 \pm 19.6%	1.4 \pm 41.2%	1.8 \pm 37.5%	-12.2 \pm 55.0%	8.1\pm26.8%	8.1%
BiLSTM	standard	64	MSE	8.7 \pm 78.0%	-3.2 \pm 159.4%	28.4\pm81.0%	-24.4 \pm 208.4%	24.9 \pm 85.6%	28.4%
LSTM	standard	64	SMAPE	-10.1\pm49.6%	-22.8 \pm 42.3%	-34.0 \pm 71.7%	-35.2 \pm 68.1%	-25.6 \pm 55.0%	-10.1%
LSTM	standard	64	RMSE	-16.5 \pm 46.6%	-18.9 \pm 43.8%	-15.1\pm86.7%	-22.6 \pm 75.7%	-16.9 \pm 78.8%	-15.1%
LSTM	standard	64	MAE	-11.4\pm57.2%	-24.2 \pm 52.0%	-33.7 \pm 94.6%	-36.4 \pm 83.0%	-26.4 \pm 73.2%	-11.4%
LSTM	standard	64	MSE	-33.7\pm113.7%	-35.9 \pm 92.4%	-47.5 \pm 313.6%	-57.2 \pm 241.7%	-56.1 \pm 235.9%	-33.7%

TABLE III

IR (%) ACROSS ALL MODEL/SCALER/BATCH CONFIGURATIONS (QF). POSITIVE = IMPROVEMENT.

Model	Scaler	Batch	Metric	Synthetic-to-Real Ratio (n)					Best (%) \uparrow
				0.10	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00	
BiLSTM	standard	64	SMAPE	1.0\pm17.3%	0.2 \pm 29.3%	-3.5 \pm 25.1%	-11.3 \pm 47.1%	0.9 \pm 22.8%	1.0%
BiLSTM	standard	64	RMSE	5.3 \pm 10.7%	5.3 \pm 25.3%	3.5 \pm 20.8%	-7.4 \pm 53.1%	7.9\pm20.8%	7.9%
BiLSTM	standard	64	MAE	1.9 \pm 17.2%	2.2 \pm 31.8%	-0.5 \pm 25.8%	-11.0 \pm 54.8%	3.8\pm23.6%	3.8%
BiLSTM	standard	64	MSE	8.2 \pm 20.0%	5.1 \pm 52.5%	7.9 \pm 42.5%	-31.8 \pm 129.9%	14.1\pm39.7%	14.1%
BiLSTM	standard	64	Pinball(0.05)	-2.2 \pm 22.3%	-3.0 \pm 18.5%	7.9\pm5.7%	-10.7 \pm 21.6%	-3.0 \pm 16.8%	7.9%
BiLSTM	standard	64	Pinball(0.50)	-0.1 \pm 0.4%	-0.2 \pm 0.6%	0.0 \pm 0.4%	0.1\pm0.9%	-0.2 \pm 0.4%	0.1%
BiLSTM	standard	64	Pinball(0.95)	-8.5 \pm 42.5%	-49.1 \pm 27.4%	-2.3 \pm 41.2%	4.7\pm8.4%	-12.8 \pm 39.1%	4.7%
LSTM	standard	64	SMAPE	-1.1\pm27.6%	-9.5 \pm 34.9%	-8.6 \pm 12.9%	-14.7 \pm 29.0%	-25.9 \pm 40.2%	-1.1%
LSTM	standard	64	RMSE	2.1\pm28.5%	-6.4 \pm 37.2%	-5.2 \pm 11.8%	-9.4 \pm 29.5%	-21.4 \pm 40.0%	2.1%
LSTM	standard	64	MAE	0.5\pm33.9%	-9.2 \pm 42.4%	-7.4 \pm 13.9%	-13.2 \pm 35.4%	-26.4 \pm 48.5%	0.5%
LSTM	standard	64	MSE	6.5\pm65.3%	-13.0 \pm 83.0%	-10.1 \pm 24.6%	-15.8 \pm 73.4%	-44.6 \pm 103.9%	6.5%
LSTM	standard	64	Pinball(0.05)	17.0 \pm 33.1%	22.7 \pm 19.5%	23.2\pm59.0%	-29.1 \pm 161.7%	14.9 \pm 33.8%	23.2%
LSTM	standard	64	Pinball(0.50)	0.0 \pm 0.6%	0.1 \pm 0.7%	0.1 \pm 0.3%	0.2 \pm 0.5%	0.5\pm0.8%	0.5%
LSTM	standard	64	Pinball(0.95)	7.0 \pm 22.3%	7.6 \pm 19.0%	-5.5 \pm 13.6%	13.4\pm22.9%	-10.3 \pm 43.2%	13.4%

TABLE IV

IR (%) FOR BIAS-VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION ACROSS ALL MODEL CONFIGURATIONS (PF). POSITIVE = IMPROVEMENT.

Model	Scaler	Batch	Metric	Synthetic-to-Real Ratio (n)					Best (%) \uparrow	Best n
				0.10	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00		
BiLSTM	standard	64	Bias ²	7.3%	7.4%	33.8%	10.4%	35.3%	35.3%	1.00
BiLSTM	standard	64	Variance	12.7%	-33.0%	13.6%	-121.6%	-4.2%	13.6%	0.50
LSTM	standard	64	Bias ²	-41.9%	-48.7%	-46.1%	-61.1%	-31.1%	-31.1%	1.00
LSTM	standard	64	Variance	-13.0%	-3.7%	-51.1%	-47.6%	-119.0%	-3.7%	0.25

TABLE V

IR (%) FOR BIAS-VARIANCE DECOMPOSITION ACROSS ALL MODEL CONFIGURATIONS (QF). POSITIVE = IMPROVEMENT.

Model	Scaler	Batch	Metric	Synthetic-to-Real Ratio (n)					Best (%) \uparrow	Best n
				0.10	0.25	0.50	0.75	1.00		
BiLSTM	standard	64	Bias ² (%)	6.5%	20.9%	-9.7%	-24.5%	4.4%	20.9%	0.25
BiLSTM	standard	64	Variance (%)	13.4%	-40.8%	58.9%	-53.2%	42.1%	58.9%	0.50
LSTM	standard	64	Bias ² (%)	1.6%	-14.6%	-14.1%	-25.6%	-54.0%	1.6%	0.10
LSTM	standard	64	Variance (%)	50.3%	0.8%	25.6%	71.3%	38.2%	71.3%	0.75

TABLE VI

FORECASTING PERFORMANCE COMPARISON ACROSS MODELS AND BEST AUGMENTATION RATIO (POINT FORECASTING).

Model	Synthetic-to-Real Ratio (n)	SMAPE	RMSE	MAE	MSE
BiLSTM	0.0	11.16	1.93	1.18	3.91
LSTM	0.0	12.08	2.41	1.40	6.47
XGBoost	0.0	7.82	1.01	0.73	1.03
BiLSTM (Aug)	1.00	10.84	1.64	1.09	2.94

limited adaptability to the real data structure. Such behavior highlights how lower-capacity models may overfit to the statistical properties of generated samples rather than benefit from their diversity.

Finally, the fluctuations observed across synthetic ratios

are consistent with prior *Train on Synthetic + Real, Test on Real* (TSRTR) studies [27], which report similar non-monotonic performance patterns as the synthetic ratio varies. Overall, these results indicate that diffusion-based augmentation improves forecasting, particularly for the BiLSTM

TABLE VII

FORECASTING PERFORMANCE COMPARISON ACROSS MODELS AND BEST AUGMENTATION RATIO (QUANTILE FORECASTING).

Model	Synthetic-to-Real Ratio (α)	SMAPE	RMSE	MAE	MSE	Pinball.0.05	Pinball.0.50	Pinball.0.95
BiLSTM	0.0	11.13	1.41	1.10	2.03	0.10	5.13	0.27
LSTM	0.0	15.37	1.89	1.54	3.70	0.17	5.10	0.56
XGBoost	0.0	9.36	1.14	0.88	1.29	0.11	0.44	0.14
BiLSTM (Aug)	1.00	11.03	1.30	1.05	1.74	0.10	5.13	0.30
LSTM (Aug)	0.10	15.53	1.85	1.53	3.46	0.14	5.10	0.52

model in this case, primarily by reducing model variance, whereas in some cases excessive or distributionally misaligned synthetic data may increase bias and degrade performance.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study was conducted on a single multivariate energy time-series dataset, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other domains or data distributions. Future work will involve evaluating the proposed diffusion-based augmentation framework on additional datasets with different temporal and spatial characteristics. Moreover, incorporating a broader set of DL architectures (i.e., Transformer architectures) could help assess the model-specific sensitivity to SD. Finally, extending the approach to **multi-horizon forecasting** would provide a more comprehensive understanding of how diffusion-based augmentation scales to longer prediction intervals.

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